

spectra of four new compounds belonging to this series were recorded and all the spectra showed characteristic common fragmentation pathways, as shown in Scheme 1.

Results and Discussion

The mass spectra of compounds **1a-d** are fully consistent with the assigned structures. In most cases, intense molecular ion peaks were observed. Thus compound **1a** showed an intense molecular ion peak at m/z 502 corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{26}H_{16}BrClN_2O_2$. The molecular ion peak was found to be the base peak. The $M+2$ and $M+4$ peaks were observed along with the molecular ion peak due to the presence of isotopes of chlorine and bromine atoms present in the compound. The formation of ion at m/z 467 could be explained due to the loss of chlorine radical from the molecular ion peak ($M-35$). The loss of *p*-bromophenyl radical and CO from the molecular ion resulted in an ion at m/z 319/321.

Scheme 2

The mass spectrum of the compound **1b** gave similar fragmentation pattern. Thus, compound **1b** showed an intense molecular ion peak which was also found to be the base peak at m/z 438 corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{27}H_{19}ClN_2O_2$. The $M+2$ peak was also observed at m/z 440. The formation of fragment ion at m/z 423 could be explained by the loss of CH_3 radical from the molecular ion peak. The loss of *p*-chlorophenyl radical and CO from the molecular ion resulted in an ion at m/z 299. The loss of methyl group from this ion resulted in an ion at m/z 284. The mass spectrum of compound **1c** showed the molecular ion peak at m/z 480, corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{26}H_{16}N_4O_6$. The loss of nitro and nitrophenyl radicals from the molecular ion resulted in ions at m/z 434 and 358 respectively. The loss of CO group from the ion at m/z 358 gave a daughter ion at m/z 330 and subsequent loss of nitro group from this ion resulted in the formation of a common ion at m/z 284.

The molecular ion peak of compound **1d** was observed at m/z 458/460/462 corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{26}H_{16}Cl_2N_2O_2$. The loss of *p*-chlorophenyl radical from the molecular ion peak at m/z 347 and subsequent loss of CO group gave a daughter ion at m/z 319. The common ion peak at m/z 284 was also observed in this case which is attributed to an ion obtained by the loss of chlorine radical from the ion at m/z 319 (Scheme 1).

The formation of major ion-fragments can be rationalized by the mechanistic pathways as shown in Scheme 2. These pathways involve an intermediary common ion (A) corresponding to M^+ , formed by rearrangement wherefrom the genesis of the major ion-fragments such as (B) and (F) could be rationalized.

Experimental

2-Methyl-3-arylquinazolin-4-ones⁴ and arylfurfurals⁵ were prepared according to literature methods. The mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol JMS D-300 spectrometer operating at 70 eV.

2-[Arylfurylvinyl]-3-arylquinazolin-4-ones (1) : To a solution of arylfurfural (10 mmol) in dioxane (10 ml), suitably substituted 2-methyl-3-arylquinazolin-4-one (10 mmol) and piperidine (10 ml) were added, and the solution was refluxed for 6 h. The separated solid was washed with ethanol, dried and crystallized from a mixture of dimethylformamide and ethanol.

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